

Right to Food Journal

From Legislative Framework to Framework Legislation

A Strategy for implementing the Right to Food

Künnemann, Rolf, Sabine Pabst & Kofi
Yakpo. 2003. From legislative
framework to framework legislation.
Right To Food Journal 1(1). 3-5.

No. 1, July 2003

The right to adequate food is enshrined in international law since the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) came into force in 1976. As much as international law is binding for any state one can but conclude that implementation of this right is still extremely poor. There is therefore no doubt that a framework legislation on the right to adequate food which would translate the obligations under international law into legal instruments adapted to the national context is a prerequisite for the implementation of this human right.

The state of the art and the options for future developments are looked upon in this issue, concentrating on the three countries South Africa, India and Honduras, which are exemplary in the sense that they

all are engaged on different paths towards the elaboration of a framework law: The new South Africa has seized the opportunity to include economic, social and cultural rights into its constitutional text. In India, framework legislation is not yet a debated topic but cases of the right to food have been taken to the courts – a *de facto* step towards the justiciability of human rights. In the case of Honduras, the need for appropriate legislation in the sense of a framework legislation is gradually being acknowledged as an important tool to ensure the realisation of the right to adequate food. In parallel, demands for a framework law have been transmitted to the FAO as part of the voluntary guidelines. Clearly, the concept of a framework law on the right to adequate food has many dimensions.

From Legislative Framework to Framework Legislation A Strategy for implementing the Right to Food

by Rolf Künemann, Secretary General FIAN International, Sabine Pabst and Kofi Yakpo, FIAN International

The implementation of the human right to food is a complex task that requires political measures, laws and programmes in a number of areas such as social, agrarian and economic policies. A framework law can guide the process of filling these gaps and provide a time table for the process leading to the full realization of the human right to food.

National framework law: Explicitly is needed!

The core content of the right to food contains the fundamental right of protection from hunger. This right is the only human right that is called a "fundamental right" in the International Bill of Human Rights. Nevertheless, this human rights standard is currently not guaranteed for approximately one billion undernourished people, although there is no doubt that adequate resources are available.

The implementation of the human right to food is a complex task. It requires political measures, laws and programmes in a number of areas such as social, agrarian and economic policies. The states parties to the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) have committed themselves to realising the right to food within their own states and in general. Some steps have already been made while some very important steps still have to be taken. A national legislative framework for the right to food could

dynamise and control its implementation.

In a certain number of countries, there are bits and pieces of such legislation but just for certain groups under certain situations – mostly without spelling out the right as such. What is missing is a clear sense of direction, a stock taking of where we are, and another crucial element: a framework law which will guide the process of filling the gaps in the current legislative framework and – at the same time – provide a time table and implementation details for the process leading to the full realization of the human right to food.

Political origins of the framework law as a state obligation under the ICESCR

The human right to food came into effect in international law in 1976 as part of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights of 1966. The World Food Summit of 1996 led to a series of political and legal initiatives for the implementation of the right to food,

which has been since then the object of a number of international legal instruments.

In 1999, the UN Committee for the Economic, Social and Cultural Rights put forward *General Comment 12 on the Right to adequate Food* as an official interpretation of the human right to food in international law. The comment describes the normative content of the right and the states obligations resulting from this right. It emphasises the necessity of justiciable remedy mechanisms for the victims of violations of this human right and the development of national strategies in order to get the respective policies, laws and programmes started. Paragraph 29 states that: "States should consider the adoption of a framework law as a major instrument in the implementation of the national strategy concerning the right to food."

What is a "framework law"?

The idea of a national framework law is a novelty in the field of human rights. It is to a large extent an agreement over pro-

cedures for regulating a complex process, which is rather easier to reach than an agreement on material contents. Therefore a framework law in a field that implies complex regulation has the advantage of getting a well defined process started – rather than trying to solve all implementation problems at the same time. However, the risk of a framework law is the indefinite postponement of difficult next steps. To minimize this risk a framework law contains benchmarks, monitoring devices and other implementation mechanisms to promote a dynamic process.

In the national context, the purpose of a framework law is to institutionalise a complex process of regulation, which requires the bundling of heterogeneous interests. This process provides an opportunity for raising the level of consciousness about the subject matter and establishes mechanisms to overcome obstacles. Domestic law – especially in the area of economic and social human rights – usually does not refer to such rights and does not see itself as serving this larger purpose. The respective legislations are rather a disparate collection of single laws and “social achievements”. Human rights are thereby barred from becoming terms of reference for legislation. Here, a framework law for the right to food can drastically improve the situation and offers new possibilities.

Contents of a framework law

The UN General Comment 12 (par. 29) introduces the concept of framework legislation:

” In implementing the country-specific strategies referred to above, States should set verifiable benchmarks for subsequent national and international monitoring. In this connection, States should consider the adoption of a framework law as a major instrument in the implementation of the national strategy concerning the right to food. The framework law should include provisions on its purpose, the targets or goals to be achieved and the time-frame to be set for the

achievement of these targets; the means by which the purpose could be achieved described in broad terms, in particular the intended collaboration with civil society and the private sector and with international organizations; institutional responsibility for the process, and the national mechanisms for its monitoring, as well as possible recourse procedures. In developing the benchmarks and the framework legislation, States parties should actively involve civil society organizations. ”

How can a national strategy for a framework law be put into place?

The process leading towards a national framework law should be driven by national civil society. Of course, at the end there needs to be a majority of legislators to support such a law. The process leading to such a majority would therefore be very inclusive and link different actors in civil society – and increasingly people from academia, government, and political parties and movements.

The mobilisation effort for a framework law could be divided into 3 stages:

1. Defining aims and human rights mobilisation
2. Taking stock
3. Legislative process

Defining aims and human rights mobilisation

On first sight, the aim seems obvious: the abolition of hunger and malnutrition. However, it goes beyond that. The aim laid down in ICESCR, article 2.1 is the full realisation of the Human Right to Food. Full realisation implies that a citizen whose right to food is violated by the state through a breach of the respect, protect or fulfilment bound obligation must be able to bring charges against the state and find remedy in the courts.

If this vision of a legally guaranteed freedom from hunger and malnutrition is shared across different sections of (civil)

society, then there will there be a chance for implementing it with the help of framework legislation. Human rights education can help to strengthen the vision in the country and politicians and leaders of civil society are especially asked for in this process. Human rights competence and legislative and administrative capacities have to go along with the human rights vision.

An important step forward would be the formation of a “National Task Force” of people from community based organisations (trade unions, farmer organisations, women’s organisations etc.), from civil society, academia and the political sphere – whatever be the case with the largest possible inclusion of civil society and community based organisations and especially those affected by the violation of the Right to Food. Such a task force would not only be able to secure broad acceptance of the objectives, but also unite the necessary expertise. Within such a context, political acceptance of the idea of a framework law can develop, and possibly cut across party lines. Stage 2 can then take off the ground.

Taking stock

A stock-taking exercise might be composed of three phases. First, in order to be able to define the contents of a framework law, it has to be identified in how far existing legislation, policies, and actions of third parties (e.g. large landowners or private companies) are responsible for destroying certain groups’ ability to feed themselves. This concerns the state obligations to respect and protect, which emanate from the ICESCR. The following list can serve as a checklist for elements to be included into in more detail in a framework law with respect to the respect and protect obligations:

(a) Obligation to respect

- The prohibition of forced eviction of vulnerable groups from their bases of subsistence.
- Mechanisms for compensation and

indemnisation in case of forced eviction already effected.

- The revision of all forms of discrimination inherent in legislative and budgetary measures.

(b) Obligation to protect

- Mechanisms for protection when third parties evict a vulnerable group from their bases of subsistence, and mechanisms of punishment and compensation in evictions already effected.
- Guarantee of security of land tenure and other productive resources.
- Effective regulation of workers rights.
- Guarantee of non-discrimination against women, in the area of work as well as in relation to ownership of property and productive resources.
- The guarantee of traditional rights of indigenous communities in relation to their natural resources.

In a second step, the state's obligation to fulfil should be scrutinised. Groups already suffering from hunger and malnutrition must be identified and the effectiveness of the state's existing policies and legislative measures to combat hunger and malnutrition in these groups must be investigated. The obligation to fulfil implies the state's commitment to immediate and long-term measures (e.g. effective agrarian reform, a basic income grant, minimum wage) towards the eradication of hunger and accessibility of these programmes to every vulnerable person. The obligation to fulfil also implies that everyone's access to these fulfilment programmes is made justiciable, meaning that individuals may sue the state if these programmes fail to deliver her from hunger and malnutrition. The following list of elements should be looked at in more detail in a framework law with respect to the obligation to fulfil:

(c) Obligation to fulfil

- Identification of vulnerable groups and causes of their vulnerability.
- Ensuring the application of legislation for minimum salary which covers the basic food basket.
- Ensuring the application of legislation which guarantees the maximum use of available resources to improve the access to productive resources (e.g. through agrarian reform) of social groups affected by malnutrition.
- Ensuring the application of legislation which guarantees a minimum income for the social groups affected by malnutrition.
- Ensuring the application of legislation which guarantees food aid or other support in emergency situations to groups threatened by malnutrition.

Finally, the framework law must contain details about procedure – the concrete steps to be taken in order to move ahead on the road of implementation:

(d) Steps to be taken

- Recognition of the criteria of progressive realisation in the implementation of the right to food in the legislation.
- Establishment of concrete steps to achieve a coherence in national legislation with the requirements of the obligations of the right to food and achieving progress over time.

The legislative process

The ensuing legislative process will require the setting of priorities. The question of resources for funding the framework legislation and the programmes to be established will be one of the main issues to be dealt with in order to succeed in the legislative process. The legislative process per se begins with the formulation of a draft law on the basis of

the above stock taking exercise. In this process, different options have to be developed: drawing up of a list of measures, prioritising these measures, financing, a time-frame and benchmarks. More specific legal measures in the future can build up on this first phase. This should be done with the inclusion of community based organisations and the civil society.

The adoption of international legal instruments for the Right to Food into national law could prove useful. The General Comment suggests in para. 33: *"The incorporation in the domestic legal order of international instruments recognizing the right to food, or recognition of their applicability, can significantly enhance the scope and effectiveness of remedial measures and should be encouraged in all cases. Courts would then be empowered to adjudicate violations of the core content of the right to food by direct reference to obligations under the Covenant."*

It should be clear, of course, that such an adoption of international law cannot replace national framework legislation with regard to the above mentioned 3 levels.

Conclusion

A framework law is a flexible instrument that allow to focus systematically on the realisation of the right to food. It therefore serves the purpose of national legal systems. Moreover, it is in accordance with international human rights law, which sees such a law as a states obligation under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights. Even if such a law may not seem feasible today or tomorrow, it is worth the effort to start building a national campaign towards this goal. This process will also generate and/or strengthen the actors and monitoring mechanisms which will ensure that a framework law, once adopted, will be implemented.